

JOURNAL OF MAMUN SCIENCE

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1

2023

«MA'MUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

1 JILD, 1 SON

ЖУРНАЛ «MAMUN SCIENCE»

TOM 1, HOMEP 1

JOURNAL OF MAMUN SCIENCE

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1

MA'MUN SCIENCE JURNALI

ЖУРНАЛ МА'MUN SCIENCE | JOURNAL OF MAMUN SCIENCE

№1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0000-2023-1>

Бош муҳаррир: | Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Urazbayeva Dilbar Abdullayevna
Psixologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари: | Заместитель
главного редактора: | Deputy Chief Editor:

Matkarimov Xamidbek Olimbayevich
Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

TAHRIRIY MASLAHAT KENGASHI | EDITORIAL BOARD | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

FILOLOGIYA YO'NALISHI (INGLIZ TILI)

Axmedov Oybek Saporboyevich

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

Galiyeva Margarita Rafaelovna

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

Kalandarov Oybek Ruzimbayevich

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Yakubov Muzaffar Kamildjanovich

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Eshto'xtarova Bibigul Bektoshevna

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti

Norboyev O'ktam Safarboyevich

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Urganch davlat universiteti

FILOLOGIYA YO'NALISHI (RUS TILI)

Cho'ponov Otanazar Otojonovich

Filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc)
Urganch davlat universiteti

Ruzmetov Surojbek Allaberganovich

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Urganch davlat universiteti

FILOLOGIYA YO'NALISHI (NEMIS)

Yakubova Matluba Tajibayevna

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Urganch davlat universiteti

FILOLOGIYA FANLARI (O'ZBEK TILI)

Matnazarov Javlanbek Kabulovich

Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

FIZIKA-MATEMATIKA FANLARI

Madaminov Bekzod Allayarovich

Fizika-matematika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori
(PhD) Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

TARIX FANLARI

Abdullayev Utkir Ismoilovich

Tarix fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Urganch davlat universiteti

Goncharov Yuriy Mixaylovich

Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Altay davlat universiteti Rossiya

Shaydurov Vladimir Nikolayevich

Tarix fanlari doktori, dotsent
Leningrad davlat universiteti Rossiya

Matkarimova Sadoqat Maqsudovna

Tarix fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Urganch davlat universiteti

Abdalov Umidbek Matniyazovich

Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD),
dotsent Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Salayev Dilshodbek Jumanazarovich

Siyosiy fanlar bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Bekimmetov Umidjan Tajimuratovich

Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi

PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYA FANLARI

Kryukova Tatyana Leonidovna

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Kostroma davlat universiteti Belorusiya.

Karpinskiy Konstantin Viktorovich

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Grodno davlat universiteti Belorusiya.

Slepko Yuriy Nikolayevich

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Yaroslavl davlat pedagogika universiteti

Xazova Svetlana Abduraxmanovna

Psixologiya fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kostroma davlat universiteti Belorusiya.

Kalandarova Madina Baxadirovna

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Nurullayeva Baxtigul Bobojonovna

Psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

IQTISODIYOT FANLARI

Ruzmetov Baxtiyar

Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Urganch davlat universiteti

Do'schanov Tangriborgan

Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Urganch davlat universiteti

Ataniyazov Jasurbek Xamidovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Toshkent moliya instituti

Sherov Alisher Bakberganovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD),
dotsent Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Matkarimova Intizor Atabayevna

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Jabborov Umarbek Rustambekovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Cho'ponov San'at Otanazarovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Matkarimov Davronbek Matyakubovich

Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Voronsova Yuliya Vladimirovna

Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi
Moskva davlat boshqaruvi universiteti

FALSAFA FANLARI

Xajiyeva Maksuda Sultonovna

Falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Urganch davlat universiteti

Xudayberganov Abidjon Adilovich

Falsafa fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Adilov Zafar Yunusovich

Falsafa fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Urganch davlat pedagogika instituti

Annayeva Nazokat Rajapbayevna

Falsafa fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Urganch davlat universiteti

TABIIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI

Yuldashev Baxrom Sobirjanevich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Ma'mun Universiteti NTM

Abdullayev Ravshanbek Babajonovich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Esamuratov Aybek Ibragimovich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Samandarova Barno Sultonovna

Biologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Tajiyeva Zebo Baxodirovna

Tibbiyot fanlari falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Nazarova Maloxat Berdiboyevna

Tibbiyot fanlari falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi Urganch filiali

Sultanov Samandar Maxmud o'g'li

Mas'ul kotib

FILOLOGIYA

1. Ахмедов Ойбек Сапорбаевич ИҚТИСОДИЁТГА ОИД ЛЕКСИК БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ ТАРЖИМА ҚИЛИШ МУАММОЛАРИ.....	14
2. Краева Вероника Юриевна СВАДЕБНЫЙ ОБРЯД РУССКИХ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ ВТОРИЧНОГО ЗАСЕЛЕНИЯ АЛТАЯ.....	21
3. Saparova Mohira Fayzullayevna THE DEVELOPMENT ISSUES OF PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN.....	28
4. Masharipova Yulduz Otaxanovna LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL STUDY OF THE NOVEL “O‘TKAN KUNLAR” AND ITS’ TRANSLATION VERSIONS INTO THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE.....	34
5. Куляпин Александр Иванович РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ И МИФ В ПОВЕСТИ ВАЛЕРИЯ ПОПОВА «КОМАР ЖИВЕТ, ПОКА ПОЕТ».....	47
6. Якубов Музаффар Камилджанович XVI АСР ИНГЛИЗ УЙҒОНИШ ДАВРИ ДРАМАТУРГИЯСИДА АМИР ТЕМУР ШАХСИ ТАЛҚИНИ.....	54
7. Махмудов Умиджан Реимбаевич НОРМАТИВНЫЕ ДАННЫЕ ПЕРЦЕПТИВНЫХ КОМПОНЕНТОВ СЕМАНТИКИ СЛОВ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.....	64
8. Аблаева Надира Кадамжановна «ТЕНЬ МОЯ НА СТЕНАХ ТВОИХ». (Восточные мотивы в творчестве Анны Ахматовой).	74
9. Марьяна Ольга Викторовна СИНТЕЗ СИНТАКСИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ СВЯЗИ КАК ПОКАЗАТЕЛЬ ТЕКСТОВОЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ РУБЕЖА XX-XXI).....	80
10. Xudayberganova Umida Komildjanovna ERGONIMLARNING O‘RGANILISHI MASALASIGA DOIR MULOHAZALAR.....	85
11. Исмаилова Феруза Исмаиловна ПОСЛОВИЦЫ О ПОСЛОВИЦАХ. ВЗГЛЯДЫ ПИСАТЕЛЕЙ НА ПОСЛОВИЦЫ.....	91
12. Джуманиязова Интизор Давлатназар кизи МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА В НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ГРУППАХ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОГО МИНИМУМА.....	97
13. Каримов Хикматбек Анварович ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ.....	104

14. Raximbayeva Yulduz Sattar qizi, Tojiyev Jahongir Ko‘pal o‘g‘li “DEVONU LUG‘ATIT TURK” ASARIDA RANG IFODALOVCHI LEKSEMALAR.....	109
--	-----

FALSAFA

15. Нарзулла Жўраев СИЁСАТ ИЖТИМОЙИ ҲОДИСА СИФАТИДА.....	115
--	-----

16. Yegane Bakhshiyeva, Ferahile Babayeva-Shukurova ARMENIA-AZERBAIJAN CONFLICT: HISTORY AND REALITIES.....	121
---	-----

17. Мадрахим Сафарбоев, Отабек Сафарбоев АЛИШЕР НАВОЙИ АСАРЛАРИДА НАЖМИДДИН КУБРО ВАСФИ.....	133
--	-----

18. Sharof Agabayev YOSHLAR SIYOSIY TOLERANTLIGI GLOBALLASHUV JARAYONINING MURAKKAB FENOMENI SIFATIDA.....	139
---	-----

19. Саидназаров Улуғбек Ахмеджанович, Рузметов Шерзод Арслон ўғли ЖИСМОНИЙ МАДАНИЯТ – МУАЙЯН ТАРИХИЙ ШАРОИТ МАҲСУЛИ СИФАТИДА.....	144
--	-----

20. Rasulov Rustambek YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA YOSHLAR BILAN ISHLASH TIZIMIDA ULARNING IJTIMOIY FAOLLIGI VA MA’NAVIY SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS MECHANIZMLARI.....	151
---	-----

PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYA

21. Уразбаева Дилбар Абдуллаевна ОНКОЛОГИК БЕМОРЛАР ИЖТИМОЙИ-ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИНИ ТАДҚИҚ ҚИЛИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	157
--	-----

22. Nyutonova Xilola Lochinbekovna MAHMUDXO‘JA BEMBUDIY “PADARKUSH” ASARINING PEDAGOGIK TAHLILI.....	164
--	-----

23. Sharifzoda Sardorbek GENDER PEDAGOGIKASINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI.....	171
--	-----

24. Xudoyberganova Maqsuda Jumaniyazovna OLIY TA’LIMDA KAFEDRA TIZIMIDAGI HAMKORLIKNI EMPIRIK JIHATDAN O‘RGANISH.....	177
--	-----

25. Allaberganova Go‘zal Adilbek qizi ONKOLOGIK BEMORLAR KOGNITIV JARAYONLARINI O‘RGANISH.....	187
---	-----

26. Jumaboyeva Mahliyo Xudaybergan qizi TALABALARDA IRODAVIY XUSUSIYATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK SHART-SHAROITLARI.....	193
---	-----

27. Qurbonova Shaxloxon Baxadirovna BEMOR PSIXOLOGIYASIGA DOIR AGRESSIV HOLATLARNING O'RGANILISHI.....	199
--	-----

TIBBIYOT

28. Абдуллаев Равшанбек Бабажонович, Махмудова Лола Иззатуллоевна ОРОЛ БЎЙИ ҲУДУДИДА ЯРА КАСАЛЛИГИНИ ДАВОЛАШГА ЯНГИЧА ЁНДАШИШ.....	205
29. Розиходжаева Гулнора Ахмедовна, Шарипова Зухрожон Камиловна АЁЛЛАРДА ЮРАК-ҚОН ТОМИР ХАВФИНИ СТРАТИФИКАЦИЯСИДА СУТ БЕЗИ АРТЕРИЯСИ КАЛЬЦИФИКАЦИЯСИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ.....	210

TARIX

30. Аширов Адҳамжон Азимбаевич СУВ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ МИФОЛОГИК ҚАРАШЛАР.....	218
31. Вахид Омаров ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ АРМЯНСКОЙ ПАРТИИ ДАШНАКЦУТЮН В ГРУЗИНСКОЙ ССР.....	225
32. Umid Bekmuhammad ANNA GERMAN AND KHOREZM.....	233
33. Кулаков Владимир Олегович РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ТОРГОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ РОССИИ С ПЕРСИЕЙ ЧЕРЕЗ АСТРАХАНЬ В XVIII ВЕКЕ.....	251
34. Ferhat ÇİFTÇİ НАУВЕР GEÇİDİ'NİN TARİHİ COĞRAFYASI ÜZERİNE BAZI NOTLAR.....	257
35. Zamonov Zokir Turg'inovich TARAQQIYOTNING YANGI BOSQICHIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA MA'NAVIY ASOSLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEYORIY ASOSLARI (qisqacha tarixiy tahlilda).....	269
36. Matkarimova Sadokat Maksudovna, Matkarimova Nazokat Maksudovna XORAZM VOHASI BAXSHICHILIK SAN'ATI TARIXIDAN (Go'ro'g'li turkum dostonlarining ilmiy tadqiqotlarda o'rganilishi).....	277
37. Скубневский Валерий Анатольевич, Гончаров Юрий Михайлович ГОРОДА СИБИРИ ВТОРОЙ ПОЛОВИНЫ XIX – НАЧАЛА XX В.....	283
38. Озодбек Раджабов МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ЭЛЧИЛИК МУНОСАБАТЛАРИНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ ГЕНЕЗИСИ....	295
39. Tahir Şahbazov “KÜLTÜREL DEVRİM” DÖNEMİNDE (XX. YÜZYILIN 20-30'LU YILLARI) AZERBAIJAN'DA KÜLTÜREL ORTAM.....	304
40. Tadjiyeva Feruza Jumabayevna ZAMAXSARIY FAOLIYATI VA U YASHAGAN DAVRNING IJTIMOYIY-SIYOSIY VA MADANIY MUHITI.....	316

41. Turaboyeva Zilola SURXON VOHASI MODDIY MADANIY MEROSI MILODDAN AVVALGI X – V ASRLARGA TEGISHLI KUCHUKTEPA ARXEOLOGIK OB’EKTINING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI MUHOFAZA HOLATINI O’RGANISH.....	322
42. Salayev Dilshod Jumanazarovich, Bekchanov Doniyor Baxramovich JADIDLAR MARKAZIY OSIYODA ZAMONAVIY TA’LIMNING ASOSCHILARI: XORAZM JADIDLARI MISOLIDA.....	330
43. Чуркин Михаил Константинович СИБИРЬ В ИМПЕРСКОЙ ГЕОГРАФИИ ВЛАСТИ: ПАТТЕРНЫ ОБЩЕСТВЕННО- ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОГО ДИСКУРСА XVI – XX ВВ.....	337
44. Matkarimov Xamidbek Olimbaevich, Sultonov Samandar Maxmud ўғли БРОНЗА ДАВРИ ХОРАЗМ ВОҲАСИ МАДАНИЯТЛАРИНИНГ (ТОЗАБОҒЁБ ВА АМИРОБОД) ПАЙДО БЎЛИШИ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШИ.....	347
45. Абдалов Умидбек Матниязович ХОРАЗМ ВОҲАСИ ЎЗБЕКЛАРИ ТУРМУШИДА МОТАМ: АНЪАНАВИЙЛИК ВА ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	353
46. Karimov Sarvarbek Otabayevich, Matniyozov Sarvarbek Sanatbek o‘g‘li QADIMGI XORAZM HARBIY ISTEHKOMLARINING ASOSIY ELEMENTLARI.....	362
47. Karimov Umrbek Davronbekovch МАХМУД ҚОШГ‘АРИЙНИНГ “DEVONU LUG‘ATIT TURK”ДА ТУРКИЙ ХАЛҚЛАР КИЙИМ-БОШЛАРИ БАЙОНИ.....	369
48. Ismoilov Shohruxmirzo Zokirjon o‘g‘li МА’МУНИЙЛАР СУЛОЛАСИНИНГ ҲОКИМИЯТГА КЕЛИШИ ВА ЕТНОГЕНЕЗ МАСАЛАСИ.....	376
49. Raxmanova Shirin Qutlimuratovna KASHTACHILIKDA RANG TANLASH VA CHOKLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI TARIXI VA AHAMIYATI.....	383
50. Rozmetova Roziyajon Baxram qizi XORAZM VOHASI AN’ANAVIY UY-JOYLARI VA ULARNING LOKAL XUSUSIYATLARI.....	389
IQTISODIYOT	
51. Xo‘janiyozov Nuriddin Yo‘ldoshevich QIMMATLI QOG‘OZLAR BOZORINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	395
52. Mavlanova Barchinoy TURIZMDA RAQAMLI MARKETING XIZMATLARI.....	403

SHARQ GAVHARI XIVA SHAHRIDA MA'MUN UNIVERSITETI NODAVLAT TA'LIM MUASSASASINING FAOLIYATI

O'zbekiston hududida sivilizatsiya va davlatchilikning shakllanishida qadimiy madaniyat o'choqlaridan biri Xorazm muhim o'rin tutgan. Binobarin "O'zbek davlatchiligining tamal toshlari bundan 2700 yil muqaddam ayni Xorazm vohasida qo'yilgan. Shu ma'noda, milliy davlatchiligimiz tarixi Misr, Xitoy, Hindiston, Yunoniston, Eron kabi eng qadimiy davlatlar bilan bir qatorda turadi. Xorazm tarixi o'zbek davlatchiligiga oid ulkan ma'lumotlar, moddiy va yozma yodgorliklar to'plangan tarixni asosi, uning qudrati va qadimiyligining tasdig'idir".

Davlatchilikka asos solinishi uchun, avvalombor, huquqiy asos bo'lishi kerak va shu ma'noda Xorazmda huquq ilmi ham shu davrlarda shakllangan. Shuningdek, Xorazm zaminidan yetishib chiqqan ilm-u fan namoyondalari yaratgan asarlar jahon tamadduni xazinasiga qo'shilgan katta hissa ekanligi barchamizga ma'lum.

Bu borada ayniqsa, XI asr boshida tashkil etilgan Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi (Majlisi ulamo) allomalarining qomusiy ilmiy faoliyati jahon ilm-fani taraqqiyotini yangi pog'onaga ko'taradi, bu faoliyat rakursini kengaytirib yubordi. Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi jahon ilmiy tafakkur tadriji, madaniy va ma'naviy taraqqiyotining benazr durdonasi sifatida tarixda chuqur, o'chmas iz qoldirgan.

Dunyo sivilizatsiyasi tarixida bunday markazlar o'zining mustahkam asoslariga, qadimiy ildizlarga egadir. Jumladan, insoniyat tarixidagi ilk akademiya, Aflotun akademiyasining "Bog' suhbatlari" – olimlarining turli mavzular bo'yicha bahs-munozalar shaklida voqelangan bo'lsa, keyingi davrlardagi ilmiy markazlar olimlarning doimiy ilmiy faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi uyushmalariga aylangan. Ushbu an'analar islom davrida yangi bosqichga ko'tarilgan. IX asrda Bag'dodda tashkil topgan ikkinchi akademiya – "Bayt ul-hikma" Sharqning to'ng'ich akademiyalaridan sanalib, mazkur ilmiy dargohda ijod qilgan olimlarning aksari, jumladan, Muhammad al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad al-Farg'oniy, Ahmad al-Marvaziy, Abbos al-Javhariy va boshqalar Movarounnahr zaminidan yetishib chiqqan taniqli allomalar va mutafakkirlar edi. Ular tomondan yaratilgan bebaho asarlar va ilmiy kashfiyotlar keyinchalik Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi olimlar jamoasining nazariy va amaliy ilmlar sohasida erishgan yutuqlari uchun ma'naviy asos bo'lgan edi.

Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, O'rta Osiyoda IX asrgacha shahar madaniyati beto'xtov rivojlanib, IX-XII asrlar ushbu o'lka xalqlari uchun buyuk yuksalish davri bo'lgan. Xorazm hukmdorlarining faol harakati tufayli XI asrning ikkinchi yarmida Ma'muniy xorazmshohlar davlati vujudga kelib, mamlakatning siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy jihatdan yuksalishi davri bo'ldi. Ayniqsa, Ma'mun ibn Muhammad (992-997), Ali ibn Ma'mun (997-1009) davrida Xorazmda davlat mustaqilligi mustahkamlanib, uning harbiy qudrati oshdi. 1004-yildan Beruniyning Gurganchga kelishi bilan Xorazmshoh saroyida olimlar davrasi tezlik bilan to'la bordi va bu davrni Ma'mun akademiyasining to'la shakllangan, gullagan davri deyish mumkin. Abu Mansur as-Saolibiyning guvohlik berishicha, Gurganchda to'plangan faqat arabiynavis adiblarning o'zi 200 ga yaqin bo'lgan.

Tarixdan ayonki, vatanimizda taraqqiyotning yangi davri boshlanishi aynan Ma'mun asos solgan va Sharqning mashhur allomalarini bir dargohga jamlab, ularga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat, imtiyozlar yaratib bergan 1004-yildagi "Dorul hikma", "Majlisi ulamo", ya'ni akademiya

tarqalgan ilm nurlaridan boshlanadi. Ma'munning hukmdor sifatidagi, davlat yuritishdagi huquq va siyosatdagi tafakkuri, ilm-fan namoyondalarini ezgu g'oyalar tevaragida birlashtirdi. Bu ezgu g'oya esa ko'p o'tmay jamiyatda o'z natijasini ko'rsatdi va matematika, astronomiya, kimyo, tibbiyot, huquq, geodeziya singari shu davrga xos barcha fanlar rivojlanib, Birinchi renessansga asos bo'ldi. Bunda o'z bag'riga daho mutafakkirlarni to'plagan oliy ma'rifat maskani – Ma'mun akademiyasi muhim rol o'ynagan edi.

Jahon ilm-u fanining e'tirof eshiticha, “Dor-ul hikma va maorif” (Ma'mun akademiyasi) nomini olgan mazkur ilmiy muassasa nafaqat Sharq balki butun dunyo uchun ham ahamiyatga egadir. Zeroki, ushbu dargohda Beruniy (973-1048), Ibn Sino (980-1037), Abu Mansur Ibn Iroq (958-1036), Abu Sahl Masihiy (970-1042), Abul Hayr Ibn Hammor (942-1018), Abu Mansur as-Saolibiy (961-1038), Abu Ali Ibn Miskovayh, (vafoti 1030), Abdulhakim Muhammad ibn Abdulmalik as-Solih, Al-Xorajiy, al-Hamdamiy, abu Abdulloh Al-Biyan Al-Naysaburiy, Ahmad Ibn Muhammad as-Suhayliy al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad ibn Muhammad as-Sahriy, Mahmud Hamid Ibn Xidr al-Xo'jandiy kabi ko'plab fan namoyandalari ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borishgani, tarixiy fakt va ular yaratgan asarlar tamaddun taraqqiyoti tadrijida muhim o'rin egalladi.

Akademiya allomalari Yunoniston, Yaqin Sharq va Hindiston, O'rta Sharqda erishilgan ilm-fan yutuqlarini ijodiy, tanqidiy, qiyosiy tahlil qilib, uni yanada yuksak bosqichga ko'tarishgan. Aynan ana shu allomalarning ilmiy faoliyati, asarlari tufayli Qadimgi Xorazmning san'ati, adabiyoti, astronomiyasi, matematikasi, sug'orish madaniyati yutuqlari jahon tamadduni xazinasiga kirgan va butun insoniyat manfaatlariga xizmat qila boshlagan.

Mustaqillik yillarida tarixda chuqur iz qoldirgan tabarruk ilm dargohining qaytadan Xorazm zaminida barpo etilishi dunyo olimlari, ilm-fan jamoatchiligi tomonidan olqishlandi, iliq kutib olindi. YUNESKOning 2004-yilda “Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasining 1000 yilligini nishonlash to'g'risida”gi qarori esa O'zbekiston hududi azaldan ilm-ma'rifat o'chog'i, ziyo markazi bo'lgani, bu an'ana bugun ham davom etayotganining jahoniy e'tirofi bo'ldi, albatta.

Davlatimiz rahbari Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2017-yil yanvar oyida Xorazm viloyatiga, xususan, Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasiga tashrifi davomida bergan topshiriq va ko'rsatmalari respublikamiz olimlariga ham ko'rsatilgan hurmat-ehtirom namunasidir. Tabiiyki, bu ajdodlarimiz qoldirgan bebaho ilmiy merosdan unumli foydalanish barobarida, ilmiy yangilik va kashfiyotlar qilish, innovatsiyalar yaratish, yoshlarni ilmga jalb etib, iqtidorli, dunyo tan oladigan yagi avlod olimlari yetishtirishga katta ishtiyoq uyg'otadi.

Bugungi kunda Xorazm ramziga aylangan Xiva shahri haqidagi ilk ma'lumotlar X asrga oid arab sayyohlari asarlarida uchrasada XVII asr boshlariga kelib yirik shaharga aylanadi. Xiva xonlari davrida davlatdagi ilm-fan, adabiyot va san'atga qiziqish yanada yuksaladi. Shaharda saroy, hovli, karvonsaroy, masjid, hammomlardan tashqari ilm, ma'rifat ulashguvchi madrasalar, qorixonalar, kichik yoshli bolalar uchun xususiy uy maktabxonalari qurila boshlandi. Bu jarayon, ayniqsa, XVII asrda nihoyatda avj olib, XIX asrda o'zining cho'qqisiga chiqdi. Xiva shahridan tashqari butun xonlik hududida katta va go'zal peshtoqli madrasalar, atrofi bir yo'la ikki qavatli hujralar bilan o'ralgan hovlisi, masjidi va minorasi bo'lgan madrasalar qurildi. Tarixiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, XIX asr boshlarida faqat Xiva shahrining o'zida 120 madrasa va 63 qorixona faoliyat olib borgan bo'lib, rus bosqinidan so'ng ular soni 64 taga, 1922-yilga kelib 54 taga kamayganligini ko'rish mumkin. Mazkur madrasalarda islom dini va huquqidan tashqari, arab va fors tillari, tibbiyot, geografiya, musiqashunoslik, falsafa, tabiiy bilimlar kabi dunyoviy fanlar o'rgatilar edi. Madrasalar davlat idoralari uchun mutaxassislar, maktabdor va san'atkorlarni tayyorlab berdi.

Mustaqillik sharofati bilan Xorazmda ilm-fanga bo'lgan e'tibor yaxshilandi. XI asrda faoliyat olib borgan “Majlis ul-ulamo”ning vorisi sifatida Xiva shahrida Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi 1997-yil 11-noyabrda Birinchi Prezidentning maxsus farmoni asosida qayta tashkil qilingan bo'lsa, 2006-yilda uning 1000 yillik yubileyi keng miqyosda nishonlandi. Mazkur tadqiqot muassasasining ochilishi Xorazmda tarix, arxeologiya, manbashunoslik, filologiya, tuproqshunoslik, qishloq xo'jaligi kabi mintaqa uchun zarur bilimlarning rivojiga ta'sir qildi. Jumladan, 2500 yildan ortiq tarixga ega bo'lgan Xumbuztepa arxeologik yodgorligining ochilishi va uning quyi qatlamlari miloddan avvalgi VII-VI asrlarga oidligi isbotlanganining o'zi fikrimizning yaqqol misolidir.

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, ulkan ilmiy meros va tarixga ega bo'lgan Xorazm va uning ajralmas bir qismi hisoblangan Xiva shahrida bugungi kunda ham ilm-fanga e'tibor yildan yilga ortib bormoqda. Xivada tashkil qilingan Ma'mun universiteti ulkan ilmiy salohiyatning mantiqiy davomi sifatida faoliyatini boshlaganiga hali ko'p bo'lgani yo'q.

Dunyo afkor ommasining e'tibor va e'tirofiga ega bo'lgan hamda shu davrda yaratilgan boqiy asarlari bilan hanuz tamaddunga xizmat qilib kelayotgan olimlarni o'z dargohiga to'plagan, ilm-fan homiysi, o'z davrining Metsenati hisoblangan, ma'rifatparvar Ma'mun nomi bilan ataladigan universitet qisqa davr ichida respublikada o'z nufuziga, obro-e'tiboriga ega bo'ldi. Muassasa yildan yilga o'z maqomini mustahkamlab borayotgani kishini quvontiradi.

Ushbu ta'lim dargohi bugungi kunda 7 mingga yaqin talablar tahsil olayotgan, Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borayotgan dastlabki va hozircha yagona zamonaviy universitet sifatida o'z mustahkam o'rniga ega bo'lib ulgurdi. Bugungi kunda universitetda ikki yuzdan ortiq malakali professor-o'qituvchilar (shundan yuzga yaqini ilmiy darajali) ta'lim jarayonlari bilan bir vaqtda o'zlarining ilmiy faoliyatlarini Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi va boshqa ilmiy tashkilotlar bilan hamnafas, hamkorlikda olib borishmoqda.

Mamlakatda xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalarining ochilishi nafaqat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'rtasidagi raqobatni kuchaytirishga, balki hududlarning iqtisodiy ahvoriga ham o'z ta'sirini kuchaytiradi. Xususan, hozirgi kunda Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda 210 ta OTM mavjud bo'lib, undan 65 tasi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari bo'lsa, 30 tasi xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari va ularning filiallari hisoblanadi. Bundan ko'rishimiz mumkinki, mamlakatimizdagi jami oliy ta'lim muassasalarining deyarli yarmi nodavlat va xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari hissasiga to'g'ri keladi. Bu, albatta, quvonarli holat, ya'ni abituriyentlarga keng tanlov imkoniyati yaratildi. Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi oliy o'quv yurtlari o'rtasida nafaqat talabalarni o'ziga jalb etish uchun raqobatni rivojlantirdi, balki ilmiy salohiyatli va bilimli bo'lgan professor-o'qituvchilarni o'ziga jalb etish bo'yicha ham o'zaro raqobat muhiti shakllandi. Natijada, o'qituvchilik kasbining maqomi oshdi, uning qadri ko'tarildi, ish haqlari oshirildi, ularga bo'lgan munosabat o'zgardi, eng asosiysi, o'qituvchilarda o'z-o'ziga ishonch, kasbiga bo'lgan ichki hurmat tuyg'usi mustahkamlandi, ilmiy tadqiqot olib borish uchun ijodiy muhit sifati yaxshilanib, natijada ishtiyiq oshdi.

Mamlakatimizdagi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari faoliyat olib borishi uchun yaratilgan sharoitlar va berilayotgan imkoniyatlar natijasida nafaqat poytaxtimizda, balki hududlarda ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'z faoliyatini boshladi va buning natijasida hududlarning iqtisodiyoti, aholining turmush darajasi, turizm salohiyati, investitsion jozibadorligi oshdi. Xususan, davlat rahbarimiz boshchiligida ta'lim muassasalari va pedagog-xodimlarga yaratilayotgan sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar natijasida Xorazm viloyatida ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi uchun yetarli sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar yaratildi va buning natijasida hozirga kunda viloyatda 3 ta nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari va 1 ta xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasasi filiali faoliyat olib bormoqda.

Ma'mun universiteti viloyatdagi oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida talabalar kontingenti bo'yicha 2-o'rinda (1-o'rinda UrDU), nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida esa 1-o'rinda turadi. Ma'mun universitetining asosiy binosi viloyat markazidan 30-35 km. masofa uzoqlikda joylashganligiga qaramasdan, hozirgi kunda ushbu universitetda 7 mingdan ortiq talaba kunduzgi va sirtqi ta'lim shakllarida tahsil olib kelmoqda. Yana bir quvonarli tomoni shundaki, universitet talabalari tarkibi nafaqat viloyatimiz aholisidan, balki respublikamizning deyarli barcha hududlari aholisidan tashkil topgan. Viloyatimizda bunday oliy ta'lim muassasasining faoliyat olib borishi nafaqat yoshlarning oliy ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasini oshishiga olib keladi, balki ularning bilimi, fikrlashi, dunyoqarashi kengayishiga olib keladi, hududning madaniy-maishiy saviyasiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Hududlarda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi iqtisodiy jihatdan bevosita o'sha hududning rivojlanishiga, yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining oshishiga, aholi bandligini oshishiga, aholi turmush tarzining oshishi, hududlarda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi faoliyati, turizm faoliyatining rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Ma'mun universitetining Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borishi

natijasida, nafaqat tumanning, balki viloyatning iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy ahvoriga o'zining ijobiy hissasini qo'shib kelmoqda. Jumladan, universitet faoliyat olib borishi natijasida ikki yuz ellikdan oriq yangi ish o'rinlari ochildi, universitetga har yili 20 dan ortiq xorijlik professor-o'qituvchilarning jalb etilishi natijasida turistik xizmatlar hajmi oshdi, respublikaning boshqa hududlaridan professor-o'qituvchilar va talabalarining jalb etilishi natijasida ichki turizm rivojlandi, hududdagi savdo va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalari deyarli 1,5-2 barobarga oshdi, xorijlik ilmiy salohiyatli olimlarni jalb etish orqali xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan hamkorlik aloqalari rivojlanishiga erishildi.

Eng samarali reklama insonlarning yaqinlariga qilgan reklamasi (jonli reklama) ekanligini hisobga olgan holda, viloyatimizga, universitetimizga tashrif buyurgan har bir mehmonda universitetimiz faoliyati, viloyatimiz, respublikamiz iqtisodiyoti, aholi turmush darajasi, urf-odatlarini, tarixiy obidalarini, bayramlari, ovqatlari haqida ijobiy xulosalarni shakllantirishga erishsak, kelajakda ular nafaqat ta'lim berish uchun, balki o'z yaqinlari bilan birga dam olish maqsadida ham tashrif buyurishlari mumkin.

Universitet oldiga qo'ygan asosiy maqsadlardan biri bu – barcha talabalarni to'liq grant asosida, bepul o'qitish tizimini joriy etish, dunyoning eng rivojlangan oliy o'quv yurtlari mingtaligiga kirish va Ma'mun universiteti brendini yaratish, Ma'mun ta'lim klasterini joriy etish hisoblanadi. Bu borada universitetimizda bir qator ishlab olib borilmoqda va "Ma'mun universiteti-2030" strategiyasi bo'yicha yo'l xaritalari ishlab chiqildi. Bunday natijalarga universitetda "Universitet 3.0" modelini to'liq joriy etish va bosqichma-bosqich "Universitet 4.0" modeliga o'tish orqali erishish rejalashtirilgan.

Ushbu ko'zlangan maqsadlarga erishmaguncha universitet jamoasi izlanishdan, harakatdan, ilm olishdan, ilm o'rgatishdan to'xtamaymiz va rejalarni amaliyotga joriy etish orqali, mamlakatimiz rahbarining, talabalarining, xalqimizning oldidagi majburiyatimizni bajargan va ularning ishonchini oqlagan bo'lamiz.

Barchamizga ma'lumki, har qanday jamiyatning ravnaqi, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, iqtisodiy barqarorligi o'sha yerda istiqomat qiluvchi fuqarolarining aqliy va axloqiy salohiyatining qay darajada rivojlanganligi bilan bog'liq. Zero, jamiyatning ma'naviy kamoloti, ijtimoiy yashash tarzi, kognitiv rivojlanganlik darajasi shu davlatning milliy mentaliteti yuksalishida, shuningdek, kadrlar tayyorlashning milliy masalasida ham ustuvor mezon hisoblanadi. Inson kamolotida, uning farovonligi va shaxsiy manfaatlarini ro'yobga chiqarishda hamda kerakli ijtimoiy xulq-atvor andozalarini shakllantirishda kasbning ahamiyati katta hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, bugungi kunda rivojlanayotgan psixolog mutaxassislariga bo'lgan talab davr talabi sifatida yaqqol namoyon bo'lmoqda. Inson bolasi kamolga yetgani sari ilmga, ma'rifatga talpinadi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan saboqni doimiy ravishda ijtimoiy muhit ta'sirida o'zlashtirib boradi. Bugungi shiddatkor jamiyatda psixolog kasbiga bo'lgan talab aynan inson omili bilan ishlashda, uning ta'sir obyektining butun hayotidagi ahamiyatini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, shaxs kamolotida turli xil muammolarning yuzaga kelishi va uning yechimi bilan faoliyat olib borishda ko'rinadi.

Jamiyatda shaxsning shakllanishi insonning o'z aqliy qobiliyatlari jismoniy imkoniyatlari u yoki bu sohaga bo'lgan layoqati, qiziqish va intilishlari, shuningdek, qadriyat va dunyoqarashiga ko'ra belgilanar ekan, inson omilining aynan shu jihatlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishida salbiy omillarning ta'sirini bo'lmasligini cheklay olmaymiz, chunki hayot tarzi turli xillik bilan bog'liqligidan tashqari, inson shaxsi rivojlanishidagi ehtiyojlari, individual psixologik xususiyatlari, atrof-muhit ta'siri kabilar murakkab hayot tarzining dolzarb muammolaridan biridir.

Bu o'rinda Ma'mun universiteti o'z oldiga psixolog kasbiga tayyorlanadigan mutaxassislarni har tomonlama yetuk, eng avvalo, boshqalarga yordam berish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish bilan birga o'z shaxsiy muammolarini oldindan ko'ra bilish va uni hal qila olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashni o'z oldiga maqsad qilib qo'ygan. Chunki, inson shaxsida, turli yoshdagi kishilar bo'lgan jamoaviy munosabatlarda, kasbiy faoliyatga moslashish, yangi ijtimoiy rolni tushunib olish har bir inson hayotida yangi muammolarni keltirib chiqarishini hisobga olgan holda bu mezonlarga e'tibor qaratish hamda jahon amaliyotining muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan, shuningdek, zamon talablariga mos keladigan jahon andozalari asosida mutaxassislikka tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tashabbusi bilan jamiyatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, tabiiyki inson qadrini oshirish, uning huquq va manfaatlari himoyasini kuchaytirishdek ezgu maqsadga yo‘naltirilgan. Aynan shu tufayli ham davlat rahbarining siyosiy irodasi bois huquqiy demokratik, adolatli jamiyatda, ilm-u fan rivoji uchun ilmiy-pedagogik jamoalarga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat yaratib berilmoqda. Negaki, davlatimiz rahbari ta’kidlaganlaridek, “Biz o‘z oldimizga mamlakatimizda Uchinchi Renessans poydevorini barpo etishdek ulug‘ maqsadni qo‘ygan ekanmiz, buning uchun yangi xorazmiylar, beruniylar, ibn sinolar, ulug‘beklar, Navoiy va boburlarni tarbiyalab beradigan muhit va sharoitlarni yaratishimiz kerak”, degan da’vatiga hamohang olib borilayotgan tizimli yangilanishlarning amaldagi in’ikosidir.

Agarki tarixdagi jarayonlarga nazar solib, tahlil etadigan bo‘lsak, davlat boshqaruvida olib borilgan odil siyosat, davlatning ilm-ma’rifatga, olimlarga e’tibori, ta’lim-tarbiya ustuvor etib qo‘yilgani o‘tmishdagi Uyg‘onish davriga xos eng muhim jihat bo‘lgan.

Aynan shu ma’noda, so‘nggi yillarda Yangi O‘zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni, ayniqsa, ilm-fan, ta’lim sohadagi innovatsion yangilanishlar, olim va ziyolilarga yaratib berilayotgan shart-sharoitlar, yoshlar ta’lim-tarbiyasi yo‘lida bajarilayotgan beqiyos ishlarni ma’rifatparvar Xorazmshoh Ma’moni ibn Ma’mun, Ali ibn Ma’munning, adolatparvar Sohibqiron Amir Temurning tamoyillariga qiyoslash mumkin. Ya’ni, bugungi davrimizda o‘tmish bilan bugun va kelajak uyg‘unlashgan holda yana Renessanslarga xos tamaddunga zamin yaratilmoqda.

Shu ma’noda Ma’mun universitetining o‘tmishdagi Ma’mun asos solgan, rivoj toptirgan akademiyasi singari dovruc tarqatishi borasidagi o‘z sa’yi harakatlarimizda dadil boraveramiz.

Nurjonov Arslon Otanazarovich,
Ma’mun Universiteti nodavlat ta’lim muassasasi
ta’sischisi, rektori, Xiva, O‘zbekiston

Umid Bekmuhammad,
PhD, senior researcher of Khorezm
Ma'mun academy

ANNA GERMAN AND KHOREZM

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10028844>

ABSTRACT

In the article, Anna German's life and activities are covered in connection with Khorezm. The reasons that why the German family came to Khorezm, their life in an ancient oasis, the situation in the period they lived in, the persecution of their father, and then the details of the family members' departure from Central Asia to Poland are studied on the basis of historical documents.

Key words: Poland, Central Asia, Khorezm, Djambul, German, Mennonite, art, theater, ensemble, conductor, teacher, repression.

Умид Бекмухаммад,

Хоразм Маъмун академияси катта илмий ходими,
тарих фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD)

АННА GERMAN VA XORAZM

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Анна Германнинг ҳаёти, фаолияти Хоразмга боғланган ҳолда ёритиб берилди. Германлар оиласининг Хоразмга қандай сабабларга кўра келганликлари, қадимий воҳадаги ҳаёти, улар яшаган даврдаги вазият, отасининг қатағон қилиниши, сўнгра оила аъзоларининг Ўрта Осиёдан Польшага кетиш тафсилоти тарихий ҳужжатлар асосида тадқиқ қилинди.

Калит сўзлар: Польша, Ўрта Осиё, Хоразм, Жамбул, Герман, меннонит, санъат, театр, ансамбль, дирижёр, ўқитувчи, қатағон.

Умид Бекмухаммад,

старший научный сотрудник Хорезмской академии Маъмуна,
доктор философии по историческим наукам (PhD)

АННА GERMAN И ХОРЕЗМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

в статье освещается жизнь, деятельность Анны Герман которая связана с Хорезмом. На основе исторических документов исследуется, по каким причинам немецкая семья

приехала в Хорезм, их жизнь в древнем оазисе, ситуация, в период которой они жили, репрессии против их отца, подробности отъезда семьи из Центральной Азии в Польшу.

Ключевые слова: Польша, Средняя Азия, Хорезм, Джамбул, Герман, меннонит, искусство, театр, ансамбль, дирижёр, учитель, репрессия.

INTRODUCTION.

In the summer of 1969, while sightseeing Warsaw, Lodz, Poznan, Gdansk and Sopot cities of Poland, Oshiq Erkin, Komil Nurjanov and a group of other Khorezm youth visited the World Variety Song Festival in Sopot. The most surprising thing for the young people from Khorezm was listening to the songs of Anna German, who was born and spent some time in Urgench.

After Anna German finished singing her songs, Oshiq Erkin also joined other to the scene to greet her and said:

- We are your compatriots, we came from Urgench.

It was natural that these words, pronounced in Russian were very dear and precious, and made her think about the far Khorezm and about the fate of her father...

While she was telling what had the young man from Urgench told her in the evening, the family inevitably talked about Central Asia, partly about Urgench, where she was born and Khorezm.

According to findings of the researcher of Anna German's life and creation from Moscow Ivan Ilichev: "According to her mother Irma Martens and her husband Zbignev-Tukholsky, the famous singer's greatest unfulfilled wish was her failure to go to her native town Urgench and giving a concert there".

This was actually not without a reason. The point was that Anna German, one of the most famous singers of those days and whose fame has not yet faded, was born in Urgench on the 14th of February 1936.

So, a question arises here as to how a Polish singer Anna German's fate is associated with Urgench.

METHODS AND THE LEVEL OF STUDY.

It is known from history that until February 1917, Poland and Finland were parts of Tsarist Russia and obtained their independence after the February 1917 political changes, but many Polish people remained in the various territories of Ukraine, Belarus and Russia. On the other hand, many German people used to live in these territories as well. They had been moved from Germany during the reign of Peter the Great, Katherine II and had remained and lived there. Among these Polish and German people, there were many families, who believed in the Mennonite Christian doctrine. Anna German's ancestors were one of such families.

Historically, philosopher and religious scholar Menno Simons (1496-1561) of Dutch origin from the Netherlands reformed the Christian religion and established his own religious group. In her memoirs, Irma Martens ("Anna German", Saint Petersburg, 2012, Amphora publishing house, page 137) mentioned that her ancestors belonged to that religious group. According to Mennonite doctrine, participating in wars by using weapons, killing people, and using weapons' force and opposing any evil was considered barbarian, inhumane and against religion. Naturally, in the times, when Menno Simons promoted his beliefs, wars were sources of enrichment and expansion of territories for the kings, military people and the religious leaders, who obeyed the other two. Therefore, the Mennonites faced severe opposition. And in the middle of XVI century, Mennonites had to move to Prussia, and in the end of XVIII century and early XIX century, some other Mennonites moved to Ukraine and Russia. Partly, in the period of 1850-1884, over eighteen thousand Mennonites moved from Prussia to Russia. Among these were the Frizens family – ancestors of Anna German.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

It is known that during the reign of Catherine II, who was of German origin, when the number of noble German people grew, start of moving of Mennonites from Prussia in XIX century caused growth of Germans and Polish people in the territory of Tsarist Russia. The family of Prince Johan Frizen, who followed the Mennonite doctrine beliefs had come to Tsarist Russia in 1850 as migrants and started living in Velikoknyazhesk territory (Kochubeev village of current Stavropol Krai).

On the 15th of November 1909, a girl was born into the family of David Petrovich Martens (1863-1922), a descendant of these migrants and Anna Martens (1886-1971). The parents called her Irma. Then they delivered Wilmar in 1911 and Gerta in 1920. Their relative Catherine, David, Henry and Hans also lived together with this friendly family. The origin of the family from the mother's side and partly from their father's side dated back to the Dutch Mennonites, but for they had lived in Poland for many years, they used to speak the Polish. Therefore, Poland was their sacred motherland. However, in XIX century, they had migrated to Ukraine, which belonged to Russia due to the Mennonite beliefs.

During those days, the head of the family - Abraham Yakovleovich Frizen (1857-1929) used to remind to his family members the necessity to continue the Mennonite doctrine. A.Y. Frizen earned his reputation and experience by managing a hotel in Ukraine. He also worked at the Bogoslov train station near Velokoknyazhesk. He was also a good carpenter and made and sold beautiful pieces of furniture. In those days, Velokoknyazhesk was a little multinational town; the majority of its population were Poles, Germans, Dutch and Russians.

Unfortunately, the First World War, which started in 1914 and the political changes in 1917 turned the tranquil family life upside down. In 1919, David and Henry were arrested by the Soviet government and shot. In 1922, David Martens died of typhoid fever. As a result, the family had to face economic difficulties. Though very young yet, Irma had to work at a chemist's shop. She finished school in 1929 and managed to enter the Faculty of Philology of the Odessa Teachers Training Institute. Owing to the urgent need for teachers, in 1930, she was issued a diploma of a teacher of the German language prematurely. But she to start her professional activities in Chebrikov town, which was in 100 kilometres away from Odessa.

But, due to the demographic and ideological policy of the Soviet government, the Poles and Germans in Ukraine, especially from Chebrikiv, were moved to Central Asia. As some quirk of fate, Irma arrived to the Fergana Valley and started working at a school. Fortunately to the family, Irma's brother had served his military duty in the Fergana Valley and had made many friends there. In addition, because hospitable Uzbek people were taking care of the Polish migrants, they did not feel any difficulties.

While continuing her teacher's activity in the Fergana valley, Irma met with Oygén German (1907-1937), who worked at the Oil refinery at Chimgan. He was of Lodz town origin in Poland, at that time he used to work as a conductor at the Chimgan Refinery musical group. Eugene spoke fluently in German, Dutch and Russian languages. Eugene was a high, blue eyed man, who had organised a library with many books, who could play guitar and could marvellously recite poetry and sing songs. Eugene was a free thinking person and his opinion was opposite to the tyrant policy of the Soviet government. He was pursued for his free thinking and therefore he had to flee from Donbass and come to Fergana Valley, which had seemed a periphery those days.

Unfortunately, Irma and Eugene's tranquil life did not last long. One day, Eugene's Uzbek close friends told him that the Secret service people had started inquires about him. This time, he pursuit and the fate made them move to a farther periphery place like Urgench. In 1934, it was not without reason that the young couple chose Khorezm. Irma's brother Wilmar had moved to Urgench from Fergana and was working as a livestock expert. In addition, the fact that here was a specific European style town of Mennonites in Khorezm led them to Urgench. So, they had not time to waste and went to Chorjoi first and from there took a steamer to Urgench. Although Wilmar had come in close relations with Mennonites in Oqmachit, he liked the idea of his sister and Eugene to live in Urgench.

The house that the young couple rented was located near the "Ko'hnaqal'a" farm market of Urgench, around the Kyrgyzyop facing the high telegraph building. If we take the memories of Yusuf Hasanov, a pupil of the first cinema cameraman in Central Asia Khudoybergan Devonov, in 1930's, the Polish, German and Russian people used to live in the houses around the telegraph building in Ko'hnaqal'a. This area is behind "Anna German" café, built facing Kyrgyzyop and around the Central Polyclinic.

Yusuf Hasanov told his son Abdulla that the Polish and Russian people from this very territory used to come to his photo studio and get their photos taken. (Probably, it were Khudoybergan Devonov and Yusuf Hasanov, who had taken the photos of Anna German's childhood photos and Irma and Eugene German's photos, which were kept safe till our time. For during those years, there were only a few photo studios in Urgench and among them Devonov's studio was most famous). According to what Yufus Hasanov told his son, next to the photo studio there used to be a barber's shop called "Zarya." The Polish and Russian people, who came to get their photos would make up themselves, visit the barber's shop to shave and get their haircut done and then enter the photo studio to get their photos. So, it is indubitable that Eugene German, Wilmar Martens and other Polish and Russians were among the clients of this barber's shop.

Irma worked as a German language teacher at the former school named after Krupskaya, while Eugene had to leave his favourite profession of a musician and start working as an accountant at Urgench bread bakery. The oblast theatre was close to the house, where the Germans family lived in Ko'hnaqal'a area of Urgench and could clearly hear the voices from the plays and concerts that were on at the theatre. Also, on weekends, Irma and Eugene used to go to the theatre named after Akmal Ikramov (currently named after Ogahiy musical drama theatre) and see the plays and concerts they thought were interesting for them. In addition, owing to their communication with Uzbek people, they started learning the Uzbek language.

Like they did all the time in their history, the Karezm people were very respectful to Polish Mennonites and treated them like any of their close relatives. It was natural that for advanced intellectual people of their times like Eugene and Irma, they may have shown interest in the words Khorezm, Amu-Darya, Urgench, their meanings, and may have asked about history, origin and meanings of the words. On the other hand, Eugene German, who had worked as a musician in Fergana, must have got interested in life and classical music of Khorezm, local dances and musical instruments.

Alongside with this, there were many occasions that the family visited the ancient parts of Khiva and got acquainted with the high minarets, the monuments of Oriental architecture. Irma and Eugene went to Oqmachit village near Khiva and established relationships with the Mennonite Germans, who had been living there for 51 years by then. So, how did these people, who were well-known as German Mennonites in history, come to Khorezm half a century before Irma and Eugene did?

It is known and we mentioned it above that the Mennonite doctrine strictly prohibits taking weapons and participating in wars. But in 1874, when Tsarist Russia was in the process of expanding its territories towards Central Asia made it mandatory to mobilise any man to the army notwithstanding their nationality and religious beliefs. And adoption of this mobilisation law by the Russians was the very cause when Mennonites started leaving Russia from 1880. Fortunately to them, the respectable and powerful Turkestan Governor-General von Kaufman and Amu-Darya division Commander General Grottenhelm were of German origin. Therefore, though their religious doctrine was different, the Mennonite Germans were invited to Central Asia, partly to Khiva Khanate. The then Khiva Khan (Feruz) Muhammad Rahimkhan II (1844-1910) also accepted Kaufman's proposal and allocated a village near Khiva to their disposal.

This was how Medemtal, Waldehim and Molotschna groups of Mennonites initially came to Tashkent, then to Bukhara and thereafter to Khorezm and settled there. One of Mennonite leaders Emil Raison met with Feruzkhan and asked him to allocate them a separate village. At the condition of not breeding pigs, the Khiva Khan allocated them some land at the Chaqirchi village, 12 km to south-east from Khiva. This resulted in 34 families headed by Klass Epp, Emil Raison, Wilhelm Penner, Jacob Janazen and Mitchel Klasson to move and settle in Chaqirchi village.

This was the way, owing to generosity of Feruzkhan, the oasis that had worshipped Islam for many centuries demonstrated its religious tolerance and allocated land to Mennonites.

According to findings of researcher Jasur Jumaniyozov, "Mennonites had their own administrative management system. The community (people) who lately were named Oqmachit Germans, was headed by Klass Epp. Klass Epp founded Oqmachit village. In this village he built a

church to perform their religious ceremonies. The church is a high white building, and served 25 Mennonite families at one time. Local population called the church “Oqmachit” and in time, this term became the name of the Mennonite village. In addition, in the village of Oqmachit, headed by Klass Epp, they had a school, a hospital, a Church and other administrative and accommodation buildings”[1].

There is much information in literature about Khorezm of early XX century. According to V. Girshfeld, M.N. Galkin: “Germans lived in Saratov province, and consisted of 142 people from 36 households” (Military-statistical description of Khiva oasis”, T., 1912 [2].

While in his work N.S. Lukoshin wrote: “There were 24 households of Germans, their houses were very compactly built and located within a small circle. From outside, the life of this population resembled some outskirts of a small German town” [3].

From the information by V. Girshfeld and M. Galkin, “The Germans were carpenters and rendered their services and supplied Khiva and Petro-Aleksandrovsk with their products. They developed blacksmithing and chimney sweeping trade”. But, N. Lukoshin noted that the works of German handicraft masters as expensive. The Cotton and Oil extraction Plant, which was founded in December 1889, is also associated with German names. By 1910, Kraft brothers took it over and a group of tinkers and masters from Oqmachit Germans used to do repair works at Ginneries in Gurlan, Yangi Urgench and Khiva.

German ladies were helpers at households of Khan’s relatives. They were responsible for milking the red colour breed cows, for processing the milk and producing butter, cream and cheese. These very German women were the first to use the mechanisms to separate milk into cream and butter. After fully supplying themselves with milk products, the Germans used to sell the excessive amounts to local population.

A group of Germans, who loved agriculture, took on developing the virgin lands. They grew high harvests of potatoes, tomatoes, beetroots, eggplants and cucumbers. The Khorezm people learned growing potatoes, tomatoes and eggplants from these Germans.

They grew apple trees, pomegranates, quinces, and apricots at the edges of gardens they had poplars, willows, elms, and oaks. The houses with windows and high frame doors were absolutely new for Khorezm people. Mennonites brought to Khorezm the first elements of construction industry, mobile machines, and carpenter’s trade.

In addition to their livestock breeding and agriculture, craftsmanship and fruit farming, they taught their children at German schools. There was a basement under the school building. In this basement, they stored firewood and fuel for the winter. They made desks from wood, each for six pupils. In addition, there was a library at this school.

At this library they facilitated conditions for running scientific research and studies. Even, the fact of bringing photography to Khorezm for the first time is associated with Oqmachit Germans. Khydoybergan Devonov (1879-1938), who is considered the father of Uzbek photography and cinema, had started his activities by becoming a pupil to Wilhelm Penner from Oqmachit. The Khan of Khiva Muhammad Rahimkhon highly valued and listened to the choir of their Church.

These very few evidences demonstrate that the Germans of Oqmachit had considerable and specific position in progress of Khorezm. In early XX century, the Mennonite Germans, who consisted of only 34 families when they had moved in 1883, turned the Oqmachit village into a European town.

Using the information in document (under number 125) “List of the summarised information about Khiva division” in UZMARDAV Archives, we find out the number of Germans in Oqmachit in 1910. This document, prepared on the 16th of December 1910, registers 137 citizens of German nationality in Oqmachit.

The years passed by, and by 1930’s this figure grew considerably. Before that, as it happened in many places of the world, a number of changes had occurred in Khiva Khanate, which was a Tsarist Russia colony. The Germans did not participate in the people’s revolt in 1916 nor they took part at the political processes in 1917. During the Khiva People’s Republic, which existed from 1920 to 1924, they continued their peaceful life in Oqmachit.

We can know about life of Mennonite Germans in Oqmachit until 1937 from the people, who saw them during those years.

In travel essays of journalist Abul Bozorov, who came to Khorezm in 1937, we can observe the activities of the Germans in Oqmachit from early X century till 1937. Abul Bozorov, who visited Oqmachit under monitoring of the district communist party committee, described the life of the Germans in the following ways: “The dates, when the buildings were built are carved with large letters and numbers on the arcs, portals of the houses. One enters the house along wonderful, dainty, neat stairs. The entrance has an immediate 8-10 steps long walkway, one the left, wide windows and there is a shining wall on the right. Here, there are places to hang and place clothes and footwear. Inside, there is a spacious hall, which is lit by the windows along sidewalls and from a triangular window in the ceiling. The floor of the house is covered with wood, underneath which there is a cellar with several sections. These cool sections served as storages. The positions of a cupboard, chests of drawers and sofas; some still have some clothing and photos of the family members. In most houses, some parts of walls and some flooring were broken or stripped out. They say that people looked for gold and jeweler. There is a hospital, a school, a library, children’s playgrounds, a theatre scene, a dancing ground, several shops. All of this was built to a plan. Each family had many writing and drawing tools and a home library. In the periphery of the town, there were many craftsmen’s shops, small companies, and a winery. The town was surrounded by walls, the end gates were guarded by armed guards.

In the gardens outside the fortress they grew apple trees, pomegranates, quinces, apricots, walnut trees, mulberry trees, oleaster trees. And poplars, elm trees and decorative oak trees grew along the edges of these fruit tree gardens. For construction and making furniture they used only the wood, which they produced themselves. The furniture is of medium quality. Havingsaid that, the cupboards, chairs, sofas and other pieces of furniture, which had been confiscated from the German town, can be found in other places of the area.

The town had a market day in a week. Only few people would be allowed from other places to that market. Meat, butter, grains, honey, fruits and other products were sold at very low prices. Later on, at the request from local authorities and citizens, the Germans started visiting Khiva market as well and selling their products there. Their good quality and branded products and livestock would be sold out very quickly. The wines, brewed by the Germans competed with the products of Samarqand and Tashkent wineries. They used to keep 30-40 years’ wines in their cellars. The Germans improved the breed of livestock and produced much and cheap products, nobody could compete with them in poultry and bee breeding.

... We have left the house garden at the lake and heading for a farm. We came across a large shed, which had alfalfa, hay heaps on its roof. These are summer livestock stalls. In the cellar underneath, they used to breed the livestock in winter. You use folding doors to enter the cellar. You face 120-150 metre long huge livestock stalls. There are four lines of food troughs. On the left straight after entrance, at the windows, there is a full size table, a chair, like in an office and a sofa on the windows side. There is a magazine, some documents and an abacus. On the sofa, there are two German men in high hats, evening suits and shining black shoes.

One of the Ollabergan Davlatyorov, who did not speak in Uzbek at all and always spoke in German and very rarely spoke Russian. The secondman was Rayim Rahmonboev, who could speak Uzbek, German and Russian very well. According to Rahmonboev, due to poverty, his father gave him to service to Germans. And somebody had Ollabergan left in the fortress when he was an infant. The German people gave the child to their manager. The fortress governor brought him up, educated him and taught him some professions; wed him and gave him household”.

So, in 1934 the Mennonites celebrated the 50th anniversary of their life in Oqmachit in their own little town. Schoolchildren demonstrated special stage shows and musical compositions dedicated to this date. In the theatrical stage shows they demonstrated the historical process of the Mennonites life from start in the Netherlands and up to 1934.

Wilmar Martens also attended the celebrations of this great date in Oqmachit and was photographed together with the Mennonites. Unfortunately such friendly relationship did not last long

– in 1937, due to refusal to join a collective farm, the Oqmachit Germans were made to move to Tajikistan and Kazakhstan.

Qozoq Hoji, an elderly teacher from Khiva told the following story about moving of the Mennonites from Oqmachit:

“I was surprised to see the town, where they lived. How did they manage to build such a town without communicating with anybody from outside, without any relationships, and without asking any material assistance?”

...One day, an inhabitant of this town showed me the house, where the leader of these Germans - Otaboy (Otto) and said: “This place used to be the reception place. Due to our respect to this German man Otto, we called him Otaboy (in Uzbek – Otaboy – the Father). Otaboy remained in town until the last day of his compatriots and handed over the buildings, equipment, property to the government commission”.

With regard to moving these people, in 1937, I was in grade five of the Soviet school, opened in Pishkanak village of Khiva district. Our school stood along the main Oqmachi-Khiva road. During that year, people started spreading news that Oqmachit Germans were to be moved to some other place. And, indeed, this happened in the end. One day they gave all horses and horse packs, all sorts of belongings of the Germans to the collective farm and took themselves towards Khiva on foot surrounded by policemen. When we went up to the street to see them, the police ran us away.

If I am not wrong, it was around 1958-1960, two stranger men and women visited the wedding in the house of a relative of us in Oqmachit – brother Samandar Qalandarov. They spoke in a language, which was strange to us. Later on, we found out that these were the children of Oqmachit Germans. This is what they said: “Our parents are old people now. They have sent us to come here and see how their Uzbek brothers were doing”.

It turned out that when the Germans lived in Oqmachit, one of them borrowed some money from elderly father Egam. One of the guests was the son of the nan, who had borrowed the money and the son brought the money to return the debt”

Indeed, bright memories were left after the Mennonite Germans. Especially, people still recall that they could easily speak in Khorezm dialect of Uzbek language, eagerly attended any weddings and ceremonies, where they were invited, that in social relations they strictly obeyed the general rules in borrowing and lending money, that these integrated and talented German people did everything in its right time and within its deadlines, and that within a short time they managed to found a European style town in the middle of Karakum desert.

In addition, owing to these very Germans the people of Khorezm oasis people learned to grow well-loved vegetable like potatoes, cabbages, beetroots, tomatoes and eggplants.

The reason why these Germans were to be removed from Oqmachit was their refusal to join the newly founded collective farms, refusal to give their children to the Soviet schools, their wish to stick to the single farmer entities and giving education to their children in their own schools.

The Mennonite Germans, who were forcefully moved from Khorezm and sent to construction of the Vaksh water dam in Tajikistan. Later on, they migrated to Russia, and from there to Canada, Germany and the USA.

Unfortunately, exile of the Mennites was quite worrying for Eugene, Irma and Wilmar. Nevertheless, they made themselves busy with their work and endured this loss with hardships. It was impossible to oppose the Soviet system. For Eugene himself had experienced pursuit, and had to leave Donbass for Ferghana and from there to Urgench, while Irma had to find shelter in Khorezm due to the Soviet government politics.

The rainy day of the 14th February of 1936 brought happiness to their family. Eugene and Irma called their daughter, born in Urgench Anna-Victoriya. The team of the school, where Irma worked and the Qo'hnaqal'a local community people also tried to help this young family, though the times were very hard.

As Irma Martens' “Memoirs” read: “For the purpose of calming the German teacher's daughter, the Urgench pupils used to visit their family”. In her memoirs, Irma cited their sincere

words in Uzbek “Апа, апа, сизнинг қизингиз чиройлик” (Sister, sister, your daughter is so beautiful).

“Our life in Urgench was tranquil, and I was gaining more experience in my teaching activity. Unfortunately, the summer of 1937 was so hot and Anna got sick. It seemed to me that my little daughter was fading away in my eyes. We had to take her to Tashkent for treatment. We rented an Uzbek house in the old town. As soon as the owner house saw Anna, he said: “This is paratyphoid fever. You must show her to a doctor immediately” and quickly put on his clothing and went out and soon returned with a doctor. As soon as the doctor saw her, he also diagnosed the same and proceeded with treatment.” – says Irma’s diary.

In her diary, Irma described much of her impressions about Tashkent, where she describes how beautiful and charming the city is, that the Park named after Pushkin is like The Hyde Park in London, that the Uzbeks in tastefully wearing skullcaps singing classical songs with China plates in their hands and how deeply these tunes stirred one’s emotions.

Irma and Anna returned to Urgench soon. Irma went on teaching German at school. Unfortunately, by that the campaign of looking for “enemies of the people” among the society got too much over-activated. During that dangerous period, many Khorezm people were deeply in grief. For it was the era, when people would tell you that your friend, who you had seen yesterday, was already arrested. According to the government order No 00447 from 30th of July 1937 “About the operation to repress former wealthy peasants, criminals and other anti-soviet elements,” the authorities activated the campaign of “cleaning” the society. Based on this order, it was decided that in Central Asian republics the operations would start on the 10th of August 1937. According to the decision of the “Committee of three,” organised at local authorities, “The total of 10700 people were arrested from the 10th of August 1939 to the 1st of January 1938” [4].

Unfortunately, due to this repressions campaign, Irma’s husband Eugene and her brother Wilmar were also arrested on the 25th of September 1937 as “enemies of the people”.

The sad thing is that the wave of repressions swallowed not only local people of Uzbekistan, but also many representatives of other nations, who had chosen Uzbekistan their second motherland. Among these were many Polish and German people.

It was confirmed by the archive documents that among the repressed were the following people:

At the meeting of the “Committee of three” on the 4th of February 1937, Lapets Arseniy Konstantinovich was sentenced to death by shooting. He was born in 1896 in the village of Pulikovo in Poland. According to the verdict of the Meeting of the “Committee of three” on the 10th of February of the same year, Bass Josef Matveevich was sentenced to death by shooting. He was born in Polish town of Tarnov in 1919. Carl Krangokovich Buchumak, who was born in 1891 in Polish town of Krakov was exiled to labour camps for 10 years. In addition, according to the announcement of the “Committee of three” on the 21st of September 1938, Viktor Carlovich Shuman, a German national, born in Rostov oblast in 1896, Aron Abramovich Rempel, born in 1886 in Oqtepa village of Crimea (who was working as a teacher of German at the Samarqand Institute), German national Erich Oskarovich Mer, born in 1889 in Latvian town of Pernov, Polish national Stepan Adamovich Eselevich, born in 1894 in Vilensk town of Poland were also sentenced to death by shooting. German national Alfred Germanovich Shturm, who was born in 1884 in Austria, Carl Frantsevich Klyaynvekhter, born in Pyakhtoldorf village in Austria, Egor Egorovich Ruffi, born in 1905 in Shendorf village of Krasnokutsk, German national Johan Fridrikhovich Tsemmer, born in 1897 in Fridental village, German national Alexander Fedorovich Shtang, born in 1874 in Fischer village, German national Georgy Kasperovich Etsel, born in 1905 in Painik village of Orenburg, German national Petr Abramovich Breil, born in the town of Slavgorod in 1873, German national Pavel Ivanovich Klauzen, born in 1884 in Leningrad, Rudolf Yuzefovich Bakhtinger-Kraytseder, born in 1891 in Sagnorden town in Austria, and Jacob Filippovich Miller, born in 1890 were all were exiled for 10 years, while German national Ivan Gotfridovich Tirbakh, who was born in Fischer village was exiled for 5 years.

In addition, at the meeting of the “Committee of three” on the 21st of September 1938, the following Polish nationals were repressed:

The list of people, sentenced to death by shooting:

- Yuzva Vladimir Ivanovich, born in 1894, Lviv town origin, he was working at “Hujum” plant in Samarqand when arrested.

- Zimmerman Zyril Gustavovich, born in 1899 in Warsaw. At the time of arrest, he was working in Leather plant No 1 in Samarqand.

- Stegenek Boleslav Edmundovich, born in 1896 in Gnezno town of Poland. At the time of arrest, he worked at the Samarqand station.

- Korzhenevsky Carl-Edmund Yanovich born in 1900. At the time of arrest, he worked in Gallaaral district.

- Stein-Rosenberg Henrich Julianovich born in 1904. From Lodz town of Poland. At the time of arrest, he worked in Qoqand town.

- Kacav Ivan Yakovlevich, born in 1897 in Novoe Mestachko town in Poland. At the time of arrest, he was working at a canteen in Gallaaral district.

The list of people, exiled to correctional labour colonies for 10 years:

- Fischer Anatoly Ivanovich, born in 1911 in Lobch village of Poland. At the time of arrest, he was working in Jizzakh district.

- Chaplinsky Kazimir Ivanovich, born in 1896 in Poland. At the time of arrest, he was working at the grain preparation office.

- Dombrovsky Josef Petrovich, born in 1889 in Bilno-Koric village in Poland. At the time of arrest, he was deputy director of a school in Samarqand.

- Godlevsky Anton Nikolaevich, born in 1906 in Gazurovo village in Poland. At the time of arrest, he worked as a mechanic at MTS-1 in Mitan district of Samarqand oblast.

- Kava Abraham Yakovlevich, born in 1905 in Warsaw. When he was arrested, he worked at the Tashkent shoe factory.

- Yushko Alexandr Ivanovich, born in 1896 in Yushko village of Poland. At the time he was arrested, he worked at a soviet farm in Pop district.

- Saniyukovich Foma Petrovich, born in 1899 in Dunish town in Poland. At the time he was arrested, he worked as a worker at Samarqand winery.

- Kharlamova Maria Kazimirovna, born in 1899 in Vilno town. At the time he was arrested, she worked as a nurse at a prison in Samarqand.

- Kruk Maria Vikentyevna, born in 1907 in Warsaw. At the time she was arrested, she was studying at the nurses training course in Samarqand.

- Kozan Vaclav Frantsevich, born in 1874 in Vishkogo village in Poland. At the time he was arrested, he was studying at the doctors training school in Samarqand.

- Kobushko Alexander Iosifovich, born in 1909 in Yastrelbe village in Poland. He used to work at the theatre named after Sverdlov. As opposed to others, he was sentenced to 5 years of correctional labour colonies.

On the 21st of September 1938, when the repressions grew worst, the meeting of “The Committee of three” the following German and Polish nationals, who lived in Uzbekistan were subjected the repression policy of the Soviet state.

The list of people, sentenced to death by shooting:

- Gaas Carl Carlovich, born in 1885 in Hamburg, German by nationality.

- Shprung Vitaly Ottoevich, born in 1915 in Urskatelsk. German national.

- Dik Henrich Petrovich, born in Dnepropetrovsk oblast; German national.

- Kurilenko Luiza Kazimirovna, born in 1903 in Novorossiysk town. Polish national.

- Kling Carl Ivanovich, born in 1909, German national.

- Vaselevsky Leonid Frantsevich, born in 1890 in Vinnitsa oblast, Polish national.

- Tissen Ivan Yakovlevich, born in 1892 in Dnepropetrovsk oblast, German national.

- Ottendorf Ulrich Germanovich, born in 1896, German national.

- Bergman Emil Aloizovich, born in 1893, German national.

- Lyuft Ivan Yakovlevich, born in 1903, German national.
- Muller Carl Willelmovich, born in 1882 in Kurlyandsk province, German national.
- Schmidt Alexander Ivanovich, born in 1883, German national...

The list of people, exiled to correctional labour colonies for 10 years:

- Shterl Oscar Reingoldivich, born in 1912 in Crimea, German national.
- Getto Georgy Iosifovich, born in 1990 in Rotgamel town, German national
- Blok Ivan Vasilyevich, born in 1881m German national.
- Schaf Nikodin Yakovlevich, born in 1888 in Odessa, German national.
- Walman Abraham Abrahamovich, born in 1893 in Khrkiv oblast, German national.
- Shalitsinskaya Augusta Augustovna, born in 1886 in Revel town, German national.
- Hegel Christian Yakovlevich, born in 1883 in Odessa, German national.
- Neyman Alfred, born in 1891 in Germany, German national.
- Yustus David Fedorovich, born in 1888, German national.
- Bertels Nina Oskarevna, born in 1893 in Switzerland, German national.
- Granider Anatoly Antonovich, born in 1892 in Germany, German national.
- Gorr Jacob Filippovich, born in 1882 in Saratov, German national.
- Bendinger Henrich Adamovich, born in 1890 in Petrovsk province, German national.
- Schmichel Henrich Georgiyevich, born in 1898 in Volinsk province,.
- Glekler Fridrich Davidovich, born in 1885 in Crimea, German national.
- Ulrich Otto Gustavovich, born in 1884 in Lodz town of Poland, German national.
- Berendts Gidvil Arturovna, born in 1898 in Revel town.
- ishnevsky Nikolay Petrovich, born in 1872, German national.

List of people, sentenced to 8 years of imprisonment:

- Vitser Ivan Ivanovich, born in 1897 uin Kharkiv oblast, German national.
- Stepanov German Petrovich, born in 1894 in Riga, German national.

On the 22nd of September 1938, “The Committee of three” sentenced Yaskulsky Kazimir Petrovich (born in 1876 in Poland, Polish national) to death by way of shooting.

The purpose of giving the names of these people, associated with the repressions era is that they were the Polish and German nationals, who were kept in Tashkent town prison together with Eugene German. It was natural that while enduring the prison tortures, they thought and discussed their lives, the causes and reasons why they found themselves in those conditions. Perhaps, Eugene German may have told them about his little daughter Anna...

At the same time Irma was hopeful to see her husband and brother freed. Unfortunately, in archive documents of the repression era, we did not see any documents about Wilmar Martens...

Many families suffered from the era of the repression, Irma Martens' colleagues in Urgench were also among them. Irma saw them at various meetings of teachers, held in Urgench, talked with them on educational topics. Below, we give a list of Irma Martens's colleagues in Urganch:

“Vall Martin Yakovlevich, born in 1911 in Andreevka village of Tashavuz oblast, a German national. When he was arrested, he was a German teacher in a school in Urgench. He was sentenced to death on the 21st of September 1938 together with Eugene German. It would not be a surprise that these two people, who had lived in one town, may have shared their views and thoughts, while enduring together the tortures in the prison. Maybe they talked about how skilled teacher Irmawas...

- Pulatov Iskandar, born in 1909 in Boyrabod village of Chorjo'y oblast. In 1922-25 he studied in Germany. When he was arrested, he was a German teacher in a school in Urgench town. Before the verdict, he was also kept in the Tashkent prison together with Eugene German. He was sentenced to for 10 years' imprisonment at the meeting of “The Committee of three” on the 17th September 1938 – 4 days before they took a verdict on Eugene. Maybe, from the threats and pressure of the investigators, Eugene felt the sad finish of his fate and asked Iskandar to go and see his kin people if Iskandar gets freed one day...

- Tevs Margarita Ottoevna, born in 1914 in Oqmachit village of Khorezm. When he was arrested, he was working as an observer at the meteorological station. Margarita Tevs was kept in the Tashkent prison together with Eugene German and was sentenced to 10 years imprisonment on the

21st of September 1938. Margarita Tevs and Wilmar Martens had attended the 50th Anniversary ceremony of foundation of Oqmachit town” [5].

We are freely writing about these people only owing to our independence. It is clear to everybody that whispering or talking about this was impossible in the far years of 1937-38, which were full of grief.

Irma was not aware of all this and thought about the fate of her brother and husband by embracing Anna. However, Eugene German and Wilmar Martens’ destiny still remained unknown to her.

Ivan Ilichev, researcher of Anna German’s life and creative activity, studied the history of this family and addressed the human rights organisations in Tashkent and Moscow. Unfortunately, for the required documents had “highlyconfidential” stamp on them, Eugene German’s life remained secret. This applied to Irma and Anna and they lived with guesses about the destiny of the head of the family.

IN Irma Martens’ diary, which she wrote in Urgench, we see the following lines about the horrible year of 1937:

“Oh, My God. They have arrested Eugene. Black clouds have covered us. It is now difficult to breathe. I went to see the prosecutor asking about Eugene and Wilmar.

- Your husband is “anenemy of people”, such people will get 10 years of imprisonment, - said the prosecutor.

- Why? What for? What is his guilt? Can I see him? –I asked.

- No!”

So, Irma’s moaning and pleading did not give any result. After some time passed, they made inquiries from those people in Khorezm and Uzbekistan, who had returned from prisons and correctional labour institutions, but could not get any clear information. One one Uzbek man told them that he had been together with Eugene in a prison and he had real hard times. At that time, some rumours were spread that “the arrested people had been sent to Siberia.” So, due to her devotion to her husband, Irma left her children to her sister and went to Novosibirsk. She worked there at a school for some time. She made inquiries about Eugene among local people, and at correction labour institutions and prisons. Unfortunately, her search did not give any result.

During those sorrowful days she had a worrisome telegram from Tashkent: “Fredrich is seriously ill! This sad news made Irma hurriedly return to Tashkent.

Sadly, her son Fridrich died of that illness. Anna was also seriously ill. The piteous situation in 1940 had a serious negative effect on Irma. But she tried hard to keep upright. Their neighbour to the rented house, an Uzbek man brought his horse cart and took Fridrich to bury.

The sadness and grief tortured Irma too much. On top of this, she had to hospitalise Anna as well. Thanks God that the Uzbek doctors quickly used their skills and improved the little girl’s state. From now on, her mother had to find a better paid job to raise a healthy daughter. She as lucky she found one. Irma Martens was invited to the evening faculty of the Tashkent State Teachers Training Institute to teach the German language. Soon after that she started teaching the German language at the CentralAsian State university (current National University of Uzbekistan). In her diary, Irma mentioned these event in the following way:

-I started preparations to enter the post-graduate degree courses. I decided to master the English. Thanks God, allthree of us – I, my mother, and Annafelt ourselves peacefully. For the owners of the house, the Uzbek family were very hospitable and treated us in a very friendly manner; they were all ever smiling people”.

Unfortunately, such tranquillity did not last long, because the Second World War started. On top of that repressions continued in a different wave. Vladislav Krauze, a student of Irma’s warned her of the threat of being arrested. Unfortunately, it was true and in the of January 1942, the door was knocked unexpectedly and on the basis that they “lived their without state registration” the IAC officers took them to the railway station. From there, they took them to Romitandistrict of Bukhara oblast. Soon after that, they were sent to Jambyl town of Kazakhstan.

Meanwhile, Ana was growing up. She could understand Uzbek and Kazakh languages, and fluently spoke Russian.

Urgench – Tashkent – Novosibirsk – Krasnoyarsk – Tashkent – Bukhara - Jambyl towns. This is the map of Irma Martens' peregrination in worries about the fate of Eugene German and Wilmar, when she was looking for them and this is part of life of a woman, who suffered too much, but this persevering lady always moved forward to her purpose. Unfortunately, Eugene's life was put an end at the meeting of "The Committee of three" on the 21st of September 1938, the year, when Irma was still worrying and looking for any information about her husband. Announcement No 12 by "Committee of three" on that day had verdicts on 56 prisoners. Eugene German was among them, the documents read that he was sentenced to death by shooting as an enemy to the people and the following accusations were used against him: "German Eugene Fridrichovich, born in 1909. Origin from Poland. German national. Son of a rich peasant, Baptist sectant. Does not belong to any party. At the time of arrest, he was an accountant at the "Urgench" bread bakery" [6].

Those ominous years made Irma and her family to move first to Tashkent, then to Novosibirsk, Krasnoyarsk and back to Tashkent, Romitan and Jambyl towns. Meanwhile, Anna grew up into the school age. Irma worried about fate and future of her daughter and gave her to a school in Jambyl telling them that her name was "Martens". And the war broke up and the people's lives grew too bad: schoolchildren had to wrap their feet with old rugs to use as footwear to go to school. Anna was not different from others and did the same. In 1943, when Irma was so much in grief about the state of the family and in worry about perspective of her daughter Anna, she got acquainted with German Brener, a Polish migrant. Soon after the meeting, they got married. German Brener was a Polish Jewish migrant, who had fled from Poland to the Soviet Union after German troops occupied the country. Owing to German Brener's marriage to Irma, her families economic situation slightly got better. Unfortunately, German Brener died very soon.

After these blow of fate, in 1946, Irma managed to obtain a permit to go and live in Poland with her family. First, they lived in Novaya Ruda, then in Vrotslav. Anna started going to a Polish school now. Already at school, Anna participated at various events owing to her love to musical and pictorial arts and got honourable awards.

In post-WWII years, Poland was also in a poor economic situation. In such situation, Irma dreamed of hiring a teacher for additional classes in arts for the purposes of improving Anna's talent, but this only remained in her dreams due to shortage of money.

However, Anna endlessly worked on herself to demonstrate her talents. Immediately after finishing school, she submitted her documents to the Picture arts department of Higher Arts School in Vroclav. But her mother and family members told her: "You can study at a different faculty and get onto picture art at the same time. You should choose some profession, which is required for the might and future of Poland!"

After that, in 1955-1961 she studied and finished the faculty of Geology of Vroclav University named after Boleslav Beruta. During her student years, she worked at the "Kalambur" Theatre and visited many towns of Poland in the theatre's guest performances.

But the love to music moved Anna not to the profession of a geologist's profession, but it brought her to the stage. She gained reputation and rank by singing vocals, Jazz and variety show genres.

Years passed by. Anna thought about her father's fate and decided to sing a song, dedicated to him. She dedicated her song sad "Гори, гори, моя звезда" (Carry on shining my star) in memory of her father Eugene German, repressed and shot in 1937 and she sang in on many stages in the Soviet Union. But Anna and her mother kept secret that it was in memory of her father Eugene. For they knew that if anybody become to know who it was dedicated to, all Soviet Union stages would be closed to her.

In the period of 1965-1982, Anna German was acknowledged as the most famous singer of the world. Her songs "Катюша", "Надежда" ("Katyusha", "Hope") and over 100 songs in the Russian language became most popular songs not only in the territory of the Soviet Union, but also in the entire world. Even the Supreme Pontiff in Rome and heads of state of many countries invited

Anna to give her concert performances in their homelands. She gave several concerts in Tashkent and Samarqand cities of Uzbekistan, where she was born and lived for some time. But, visiting Urgench, travelling in Khorezm, where she was born and spent her childhood remained an unfulfilled wish and dream for Anna. For on the 27th of August 1967, the injury she had from a car accident in Italy prevented her from going to the far away Urgench. Anna received treatment and recovered in Constanchin town clinic and returned to the stage in 1969.

Her concerts programs all over the world continued in colossal success. Her songs were welcomed with great ovations in the famous concert halls of Europe, Soviet Union, Australia, the USA, and Canada. These included her song, devoted to the memory of her father “Гори, гори, моя звезда” (Carry on shining my star).

On the 23rd of March 1972 Anna got married to Zbignev Tukholsky. In three years, on the 27th of November 1975, her son Zbignev (Zbmshek) Ivarr Tukholsky was born in Warsaw. As Zbmshek grew, as Anna embraced him she felt she saw her father Eugene German, and this state of her soul inspired her to sing the “Гори, гори, моя звезда” (Carry on shining my star) song on stages, within the family. While the stage performance continued receiving greater and louder ovations.

In the year 1979, which was full of fame and happiness, and life celebrations, Anna came to Tashkent and planned a trip to Urgench. Unfortunately, her sickness aggravated again and pains tortured her again, and the doctors did not allow her making a trip to far away Khorezm.

However, not only in 1979, but also Anna German managed to get acquainted and had a brief talks with Khudoyor Ollayorov, who was from Khiva and was working as a consultant at the Soviet Union Central Teleradio Company, and professor at the Moscow State University during her concert tours in Moscow, and in 1972 in Novosibirsk - with Ozod Husayinov from Khonqa district, an environmental protection scholar, who went to Novosibirsk on a business trip. She told them about her dream to visit Urgench and her plan to give a concert there.

Unfortunately, this dream of Anna German remained a dream only. The singer, who was famous in her days and whose fame has not been faded nowadays, died of a bad illness on the 25th of August 1982. She was only 46 then.

THE KHOREZM PEOPLE, WHO MET WITH ANNA GERMAN “...I COULD NOT VISIT URGENCH”

Doctor of medical sciences, professor Khudoyor Ollayorov was born in Khiva town of Khorezm oblast and studied at the Medical Institute in Samarqand. Over a year, he worked at the Khiva hospital. After 1957, he worked at the “Uzbekistan” Sanatorium in Yalta, from 1961 he conducted research work at the Moscow Medical Institute, and Moscow State University. He worked as a consultant at the Central Television and checked the voice of TV presenters, journalists and treated them if they were sick. He made friends with Levitan, Nikulin, who were extremely famous of the time and his memories about them were published in Uzbekistan and abroad. Professor Khudoyor Ollayorov’s medical scientific works were published in 137 countries in 29 languages.

He is one of the Khorezmorigin people, who managed to talk with Anna German during his work at Central Television.

“On a day in 1978, poet and journalist Alexander Lvovich Jigarev came to Central TV, where I worked and asked me to join him to the “Melodiya” studio. The studio “Melodiya” planned recording Anna German’s songs, but from the morning the singer’s voice was strangely broken and he asked me to see what I could do with her throat. It was natural for it was my daily job at the Central TV.

I knew Alexander Jigarev very well for not only I read his poems and articles often, but also he frequently visited Central Television. He knew very well that I was an Uzbek doctor, from Khorezm. When we walked into the Studio, we saw famous singer Anna German with her throat bandaged.

- Here is doctor Ollayorov. He will find the remedy to your malady, - said Jigarev right after we passed through the door.

At that moment, Anna, who was gently feeling the kerchief over her throat, stared at me with astonishment and said:

- Hello, are you an Uzbek? Which part of Uzbekistan are you from? –asked her. This brief talk let me feel that she was wheezing.

- Yes, I am an Uzbek. From Khorezm! –I said.

As soon as she heard my words, she stood up and stretched her hand to me and greeted me again.

- Uzbekistan, Khorezm – is my second motherland. For I was born in Urgench, - she said.

To be honest, although I had listened Anna’s songs, I had not paid any attention to her biography.

- It is unexpected news for me. It is so much pleasant for me hear the word Khorezm from you, - I said.

Although Jigarev seemed glad from what we were talking about, he also seemed a little worried. It was natural, he wanted me to immediately check Anna’s voice and treat her. I immediately attended my duties.

On the following day, Anna German came to central Television together with Jigarev. They thanked me and went into the shooting room to get the TV programme filmed. They had a vrief talk on TV and they recorded her songs “Ждите весну”, “Останься”, “Идет ребёнок по земле” (Wait for the spring, Please, stay, The child is walking on the Earth). On the way out from television, the film director and I saw Anna off. Anna left us invotation tickets to her concert. I went to the concert with my family and gave her bunch of flowers and a “Khiva” booklet. While accepting oour gifts, she said:

“This man is doctor Ollayorov from the land of Khorezm, where I was born”, and the hall roared with applause.

I recall, in 1979 and 1980 Anna German’s concerts were organised in Moscow and other cities. This time I was away in foreign countries. And I could not attend her concerts. But when one of her closest friends poet Jigarev came to Central TV or at any other events, we would meet and our conversation would lead to Anna. At one of such meetings, Alexander Jigarev told me that he was writing a book about the facts that Anna was born in Khorezm and lived there for some time, and in general - about Anna’s life and creative activities. He made inquiries about information, associated with Khorezm. I told him everything I knew about Khorezm, Urgench and Khiva and invited him at his first convenience to visit the oasis, where Anna was born.

25th of August 1982. The day Anna German died. As soon as I heard this sad news, I rang Jigarev to offer condolences to him. I did not find him at home. Sometime later, I saw him at an event in Ostankino and offered condolences to him. Jigarev told me with sorrow that he had no time to publish the book he was writing while Anna was still alive amd was unable to find time to go to Urgench.

- Now, I will publish a complete book in her memory and you will be one of the first to get a copy, - said Alexander.

In 1988, “Iskusstvo” Publishing house printed Alexander Jigarev’s book “Anna German”. Sadly enough, just before it was published Jigarev himself died. So I did not get any copy from his hand but bought one in a bookshop. It is in my personal library now. Every time I take this book or if I read anything about Anna German in mass media, I recall our talks at Central Television and Jigarev’s words “I could not go to Urgench”.

Both Anna German and Alexander Jigarev’s memories are always in my heart [7].

“ANNA SAID “THANK YOU” IN UZBEK...

Ozod Husayinov was born in 1938 in Khonqa district. He studied at Novosibirsk Institute of Trade. For many years, he occupied official positions at trade organisations in Khorezm oasis. In addition, he studied the environmental issues, the situation at the Aral Lake and the surrounding territories, he developed scientific designs of brining water to Aral from the Caspian Sea, in addition, he evaluated proposal-designs of taking water to undeveloped areas of Kazakhstan, Mongolia, China, Arab countries and Russia.

Ozod Husayinov is another of the few people from Khorezm, who succeeded to meet Anna German.

“From my childhood, I was interested in history, nature, and music. During my university years in Novosibirsk, I got interested in history of people in Siberia and gathered much information

about history, which was outside my professional field. It is generally known that in 1930-53, there were many prisons in Siberia. In the 1960s, when I studied in Novosibirsk, most victims of repressions were freed from these prisons and rehabilitated. Most of my fellow students in our group were Siberians, when we visited their families, along talks, their parents would inevitably start speaking about repressions. On a day, when we were listening to the radio in the house of my group-mate Vasily Matveev, a radio program gave some songs of Anna German and the journalists spoke about her. I was astonished to hear that Anna German was born in Urgench. The Urgench reminded me of my Khjarezm and my longing grew worse.

So, our golden student years passed. In 1972, I went to Novosibirsk to visit my group-mate friends. We made some inquiries and found out that Anna German was giving a concert in the city. By that time, through mass media and TV broad public already knew Anna German's name, and that she was born in Urgench. We, a group of 14 people, bought a big bunch of flowers for the famous singer and went to her concert. The concert was a great success. I went on to the stag to give Anna the flowers. When I approached Anna I was so overexcited that dropped my handkerchief on the stage. I bent to pick my handkerchief up saying in Uzbek "that was a big miss" without knowing that I was speaking Uzbek. So, when I handed the flowers to Anna, for some reason, she looked at me with a surprise and took the microphone a little away from her and said quietly: "Are you an Uzbek?" I said loudly: "Yes, I am an Uzbek. I studied in Novosibirsk. I am from Khorezm, where you were born." Anna's eyes shone with happiness and took the microphone and said: "This man (of course, she had quietly asked for my names) is comrade Ozod Husayinov. He has come to my concert from Uzbekistan, where I was born and grew. I am very happy for that." I was so excited and said "Thanks" (Spasibo) in Russian. But Anna said "Thanks" (Rahmat) in Uzbek and the audience roared in ovations.

That evening, I treated my group-mates at a restaurant only because that Anna German said thank in Uzbek (rahmat).[8]

CONCLUSION.

"Anna German did not visit Khorezm! As you say, she was born in Urgench and lived there for over 2 years. And some family photos taken during those years have been kept safe. What would change even if she visited Urgench after the concerts in Samarqand and Tashkent?" asked a friend of ours, who thought he was an intellectual.

Poet and historian Khurshid Davron was also asked a similar question many years ago in 1990s: "Is it necessary to write about Bibikhanum? So, what importance does it make, if she was together with Amir Timur? Is it required to write about her for that?"

This friend of mine was noted for his slight egoism for he would cut right away and never fear of fighting for his purpose. I did not say anything to him. I did not utter a word to him for looking into his eyes, full of firmness and conceit, I realised that whatever argument I would bring would not change his beliefs.

Is it really necessary to write all the trifles that happened in the past? Who needs them? What is the purpose they serve to?

It is generally known that the history of our people had witnessed tragic and horrible events. However, the past is not only collection of tragedies and black periods, or not only great discoveries, bloody whippings and revolutions. It also consists of important personalities and events that were support and pillar of certain eras of our history, which seem trifle to others.

This history saw Amir Timur, who defeated great kings but was a "obedient captive" of beautiful Saroymulkhanum, Turkon khatun, who due to her pride thought Jaloliddin and her Turkmen mother enemies and preferred leftovers of Genghiz Khan, wretch Abdulatif, who killed his own father for want of crown, and Saidkhon Karimkhonov, who captured Bobon Botir and submitted him to Tsarist government soldiers, when Bobon raised a revolt against the enemy. History is never lessening lessons not only wisdoms and heroism of great personalities, but also cowardice of weak people, impudence of idiots, swindling of cunning people and deception of naïve people by others naïve.

Blaise Pascal said once: “If Cleopatra’s nose had been shorter, the whole face of the Earth would have changed”. This being so, the fact that Bibikhanum was trusted education, upbringing of Timuride princes makes it clear how serious her position was in the kingdom, created by Amir Timur. Therefore, would it fair, if we don’t write about the influence the queen had to development of the kingdom, i.e., to development of our history?

Of course, there is a counter argument to what Pascal said about Cleopatra’s nose shape. Great Japanese writer Akutagawa Ryunosuke said the following: “Even if Cleopatra’s nose had been shorter, it is not out of exception that Antony wouldn’t have noticed it. Even if he saw and knew it, he would have found some feature in her that would have replace this. Even if we turn the entire world upside down we cannot find a woman with the qualities, better than those of our beloved one. Like we are mesmerised by our beloved woman, Antony would have found some quality in Cleopatra that would have covered any shortfall in her eyes or lips. On top of this, we can say: “And what about heart?” It is natural that the ones we love have the highest and purest hearts. Her clothes, wealth and position in society all apply to her positive features. There even were some cases in life that the rumours that some great person had loved her once, was considered a positive feature.

Cleopatra was the last queen of Egypt who was used to grandeur and secrets. When she had a priceless crown on her head and held a water lily or some other flower in her hand and spread fragrance to the entire world, would anybody, especially Antony notice that her nose was slightly shorter?

This kind of self-deception is not applicable only to love. Only sometimes, we see the world in colours we love. For instance, let’s take the case at the reception door of a dentist’s room.

No matter how hard we try, how eagerly we wish to imagine that moment to forget our toothache for a moment, it is clear that we cannot imagine it. Of course, toothaches have nothing to with world history. But, politicians, who want to know the mood of people, the military people, who love to find out the situation of the enemy, the businessmen, who want to be aware of the financial situation all tend to fall into this self-deception. I cannot refuse that intellect and wisdom makes corrections to this situation. In addition, I also admit that there is “fortuity”, which manages all human affairs. Maybe, self-deception is an eternal force that manages human history.

In sort, the past two thousand years human history did not depend on the shape of Cleopatra’s nose, and she was only a moment’s glimpse in human history. It is more dependent of our stupidity. Ridiculous, but great stupidity.”

I think, the answer to the question of “Is it necessary to write about Bibikhanum?” can also be found in the history of Cleopatra’s nose.

“One day, we had to bury a child, who only lived for two days in this world... Its mother was fighting for her life in bed and did not know that heer child was dead. And when we went to the graveyard for burial, the child’s father, who was very young and inexperienced, and was astonished by this unknown, unclear, merciless and murderer blow looked at me and my friend in grief as if asking for a comment on the secret and cause of that disaster. My friend was an experienced man and he was consoling him with the following words:

- “It is nothing for much worry, my friend. You got a long life to live yet, and your children are at your waist. And do not torture yourself for a kilo and half flesh.” I don’t know about the young father, but such consolation drilled a deep pain into my soul.

The death of the infant, who did not see any sufferings and tortures, pleasure and happiness of this temporary world seemed nothing in front of the enormous and sophisticated secrets, terrible tragedies of our era. But has the responsibility of Iman and conscious to live in this world been always useless in front of simplest secrets and events? Isn’t this uselessness the main criterion of human fate?

Our ancestors said: “Death is inevitable and fair!” I do not deny this. But I also know that not any death is inevitable and fair. Several years will pass and the infant, who we have buried will become part of the past. Those, who say that this will not happen, are mistaken. Thus, a simplest thing, for example, Cleopatra’s nose, lack of a little finger on Bibikhanum’s hand can determine our attitude to history.

The past and today are not some thread, which is tied together; they are knotless chain that is existent from the beginning. Any sin, committed in the past applies not only to those far away sinners, but also us. For any kind deed, committed in the past, the future people will enjoy the good fruits of it. The only thing that links the past and today is future.

One of the happiest moments in this world is planting a tree. A black hearted man would never plant a tree. A man, who has plants a tree does this not only for himself, but for his children and grandchildren, who are already born and have to be born yet. While history is a garden of our ancestors. As the years and centuries pass, people will feel that some tree is missing in this garden. And this missing tree may be the tree, which we have not managed to plant today” – writes Khurshid Davron while deeply thinking and suffering from the above question.

If we go back to aspirations of Anna German towards going to Khorezm. Not only Anna German, but during the ancient history of the world this beautiful and magic oasis of Khorezm fascinated Alexander the great and Qutayba, Genghiz Khan and Peter the Great, and Bekovich-Cherkassky and many other conquerors. In some cases, scholar like Arminy Vamberi from Hungary visited Khorezm by concealing their names and intentions.

In short, in aspiration to Khorezm, travellers like Ibn Batuta, secret agents like Jenkinson, who was sent by Ioan Grozny and representative of different trades came to this oasis and write what they saw in this land. All these sources are rare manuscripts that help study the history of Khorezm by comparing them with other sources.

This world is a paradox place. This magic oasis was occupied by invaders with their intention of ill will and weapons in their hands; and all sorts of traders came here for the want of profit and secret spies came here by hiding their real names and intentions. Unfortunately, Anna German, who was born herein Urgench and lived for some time, and who greatly contributed to development of world arts and improvement of human thought could not return to this sacred land.

Yes, Anna German longed for Khorezm all her life. The reason of our sorrow is that, had she managed to come back to Khorezm, she would have left her magic memories on the basis of their life here like in her tales for little children. Maybe, owing to the works, written by this highly intellectual woman, another work would have been written about Khorezm. Maybe, some poems would have been written about Urgench, about Khorezm oasis...

However, the fact that Anna German longed for Khorezm oasis, and that she was born in Urgench is a serious issue. Many documentary and feature films, serials were created when she was alive, and have been and are created after her death; books and articles are written. And the fact that Anna German was born in Urgench, her father Eugene German was repressed in Khorezm are written in the books and depicted in the films. Thus, with the help of the book written and the movies taken the fame of Urgench is spread to the world in the person of Anna German. In addition, there is a good two-storeyed a restaurant named after Anna German in Urgench, in that territory of the city, where a group of Polish, German and Russian people used to live in 1935-37. And this is serving a symbol of friendship of the two nations.

To my mind, for the purposes of strengthening this friendship, one of the hotels to be built in Urgench or Khiva, which is famous in the world as an open air museum – an Oriental pearl and one of the cinemas or amphitheatres to be built in Khorezm should be named after Anna German. For in the very Khiva the first photo and cinema cameraman in central Asia Khudoybergan Devonov learned the art of photography and cinema from the Oqmachit Mennonite Germans. And Anna German's ancestors from mother's side were of Mennonite belief. In addition, in a historical document about Anna German's father Eugene German, he is mentioned as a German national. In addition, it is necessary to build an avenue in Urgench, where Anna German was born and call it after her name, and install a monument or a portrait sculpture to her. Thus, construction in our oblast of a hotel, cinema, museum or an avenue, associated with Anna German's name, would serve to additional improvement of cultural relations between our country and Poland, Germany and Russia. We would recommend Uzbek cinematographers to produce a film about Anna German, for Anna German's life and creative activities, and the entire issue is a ready screen play for a serial.

In addition, on the 14th of February, on the day Anna German was born, it is necessary to organise a scientific-practical forum, a festival for youth in Urgench. The main thing is that it would be expedient to take some soil from Urgench to Anna German's grave in Poland. It is also necessary to translate the fairy tales, Anna German wrote for children, all her interviews, including about Urgench, about Uzbekistan, the books and articles about her should be translated and printed in Uzbek. It would be wonderful if the documentary and fiction films about this famous singer are translated and demonstrated on television of our country. It is known that famous journalist Ivan Ilichev from Moscow worked hard to study and promote life and creative heritage of Anna German and published several books about the singer in Russia. In addition, on the 26 thfo February 2018, at the initiative of I. Ilichev and Olgana, Anna German's fans from Khorezm Manzura Hikmatova, Zulfiya Madaminova, Valery Strazhalkovsky held an Anna German's memorial evening in Urgench. I think, holding of such eventsshould become a tradition. The relations of friendship between Uzbek and Polish people would be raised to a higher level if an Uzbek-Polish Cultural Relations Society named after Anna German is founded to implement all the aforesaid activities.

These thoughts are my personal opinion only.

These are my answers to the question from a friend of mine, which I mentioned in the beginning of the conclusions. I think, writer Khurshid Davron gave a wonderful description of the other issue. Please, give your assessment of the degree of our research of the issue of Anna German and Khorezm and Anna German and Urgench.

References / Иқтибослар / Сноски

1. "The Youth of Kharezm" newspaper ("Хоразм ёшлари"), 19 th of June 2009.
2. "Военно-статистическое описание Хивинского оазиса". -Т.: 1912 г. -стр.6.
3. О современном состоянии Хорезмского ханства". ЦГА РУз, ф 2, оп 1, д 314, л 48.
4. Шамсутдинов Р., Курбонов Х., Бекмухаммад У. "Қатағон қурбонлари. 5-китоб. -Т.: "Шарқ" нашриёти, 2012. -5-бет.
5. Шамсутдинов Р., Курбонов Х., Бекмухаммад У. "Қатағон қурбонлари" 5 китоб. -Т.: "Шарқ" нашриёти, 2012. -14 бет.
6. Шамсутдинов Р., Курбонов Х., Бекмухаммад У. "Қатағон қурбонлари" 5 китоб. -Т.: "Шарқ" нашриёти, 2012. -368 бет.
7. Бекмухаммад У. Анна Германнинг армонлари, "Хоразм" нашриёти, Урганч, 2019. -14 бет.
8. Бекмухаммад У. Хоразм ва хоразмликлар. Биринчи китоб. -Бухоро., "Дурдона" нашриёти, 2022. -35 бет.

«MAMUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

1 JILD, 1 SON

ЖУРНАЛ «MAMUN SCIENCE»
TOM 1, HONEP 1

JOURNAL OF MAMUN SCIENCE
VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000